

Novafert

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D3.6 – Three policy briefs

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Abbreviations

ABP: Animal By-Product

CAP: Common Agricultural Policy

CEAP: Circular Economy Action Plan

CMC: Component Material Categories

EBA: European Biogas Association

FPR: Fertilizing Products Regulation

JRC: Joint Research Centre

INMAP: Integrated Nutrient Management Action Plan

RENURE: Recovered Nitrogen from Manure

Executive Summary

Deliverable 3.6 (D3.6) aims to provide policy recommendations that address the barriers and challenges currently hindering the adoption of circular fertilisers across Europe. The policy briefs included in this deliverable consist of two jointly formulated documents and recommendations derived from the NOVAFERT policy session organised at FER-PLAY-play final event. These recommendations are based on an in-depth analysis of existing regulatory frameworks and discussions with stakeholders involved in nutrient recycling and circular economy practices. The policy brief includes targeted recommendations designed to support the widespread uptake of circular fertilisers and facilitate the integration of these products into mainstream agricultural practices.

As part of this deliverable, a joint policy letter has been drafted by the NOVAFERT project, in collaboration with several key EU stakeholders including the European Biogas Association (EBA), COPA-COGECA, and three other European consortia focusing on nutrient recycling: Nutri2Cycle, FERTIMANURE, and NUTRI-KNOW. This open letter calls for the safe use of digestate into the Integrated Nutrient Management Action Plan (INMAP). The letter highlights digestate's role in nutrient recycling, resource efficiency, and its potential to reduce reliance on synthetic fertilisers.

The policy brief also addresses the importance of the Soil Monitoring Law and its potential role in facilitating the integration of circular fertilisers into soil health restoration and sustainable land management practices. The brief highlights the need for stronger support for the circular economy, clearer guidelines on nutrient recovery, and the role of circular fertilisers in contributing to the EU's Green Deal and sustainability targets.

Additionally, the deliverable includes a comprehensive policy brief derived from the NOVAFERT-led workshop at the FER-PLAY final event, which addresses key regulatory challenges faced by the circular fertiliser market. This workshop gathered insights and expertise from various stakeholders to directly respond to the regulatory frameworks that impact the production, application, and market uptake of circular fertilisers in the EU.

1. Introduction

The European agricultural sector faces increasing pressures to improve sustainability, reduce its environmental footprint, and transition towards more circular and resource-efficient practices. One of the major challenges is the need to reduce the reliance on synthetic fertilisers, which contribute significantly to environmental pollution, soil degradation, and the depletion of natural resources. Circular fertilisers, derived from organic waste, agricultural by-products, and other nutrient-rich materials, present a promising solution to this challenge by recycling nutrients and enhancing soil health.

However, the widespread adoption of circular fertilisers in Europe is hindered by several regulatory and market barriers. These include inconsistent legislation, lack of clear guidelines, and gaps in the recognition and promotion of circular fertilisers in key EU policies. Without proper support and an enabling regulatory framework, the transition to circular fertilisers risks stagnation, limiting their potential to contribute to environmental sustainability and the EU's broader climate and circular economy goals.

Several European projects (funded mainly under Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe programmes) are currently evaluating the efficiency and environmental safety of potential CE-marked alternative fertilizer products across various growing conditions, including their impacts on soils, water, and air, in line with the "Farm to Fork" and "Biodiversity" European strategies published in May 2020. NOVAFERT aims to bring together the required information for the effective and safe use of fertilizing products in order to facilitate decision-making on valorisation employed for nutrient recovery, based on actual demands at the regional and market levels throughout the EU.

To address these challenges, the NOVAFERT project, in collaboration with other European initiatives, has taken a comprehensive approach that combines research, stakeholder consultation, and policy development. This policy deliverable aims to provide actionable recommendations to policymakers at the EU and national levels, addressing the barriers to the adoption of circular fertilisers and promoting the creation of a more enabling policy environment.

This policy brief includes a detailed analysis of the regulatory challenges currently facing the circular fertiliser market, with a focus on key pieces of legislation (Fertilising Products Regulation (FPR), and the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). It also discusses the role of the Integrated Nutrient Management Action Plan (INMAP) and the European Green Deal in driving nutrient recycling and sustainable agriculture. By examining these key regulatory frameworks, the brief identifies gaps and inconsistencies that hinder the uptake of circular fertilisers and provides policy recommendations to address these challenges.

In addition, a significant aspect of this policy brief is the inclusion of feedback on the proposed Soil Monitoring Law, a crucial regulatory tool for enhancing soil health and promoting sustainable land management practices. As part of this initiative, the NOVAFERT and FER-PLAY projects call for specific amendments to the Soil Monitoring Law, recognizing the role of circular fertilisers in improving soil quality, enhancing carbon sequestration, and reducing

dependency on synthetic fertilisers. This law aims to protect and restore the health of European soils, which are critical for food security, biodiversity, and overall ecosystem services. The brief advocates for binding targets, the inclusion of circular fertilisers as a core element in soil regeneration practices, and the creation of a clear framework to guide Member States in implementing sustainable soil management practices.

The topics covered in this policy deliverable include:

- The regulatory barriers to the adoption of circular fertilisers.
- The importance of integrating circular fertilisers into broader sustainability frameworks such as INMAP and the European Green Deal.
- The proposed amendments to the Soil Monitoring Law to encourage the use of circular fertilisers in soil health restoration and nutrient recycling.
- The need for clearer guidelines and harmonized standards across Member States to enable the safe and effective use of circular fertilisers.

The significance of this policy deliverable lies in its potential to influence EU and national policies, creating a more supportive environment for circular fertilisers. By addressing regulatory gaps and promoting the integration of circular solutions into agricultural practices, the recommendations aim to reduce nutrient losses, improve soil health, enhance resource efficiency, and contribute to the EU's climate and sustainability goals.

2. Joint position paper on the safe use of Digestate in the INMAP

OPEN LETTER

Unlocking the safe use digestate in the INMAP: an opportunity for nutrients recycling and on-farm circularity

The cosignatories include COPA-COGECA, which represents over 23 million farmers and 22,000 agricultural cooperatives and the European Biogas Association, which represents nearly 8000 stakeholders from the biogas and biomethane value chain in Europe, as well as two European projects focusing on nutrients recycling and digestate – Nutri2Cycle and **NOVAFERT**.

The need **to reduce dependency on nitrogen fertilisers by diversifying the sources of fertilisers and developing the supply of sustainable fertilisers** has gained urgency following Russia's war on Ukraine. **Using fossil-free, low-carbon, recycled nutrients to produce organic fertilisers will also accelerate the decarbonization pathway to a net-zero Europe.** These challenges were outlined in the communication of the Commission on Safeguarding food security and reinforcing the resilience of food systems from November 2022 as well as in the resolution of the European Parliament on the availability of fertilisers in the EU from February 2023. Yet, to date, digestate faces a major barrier in the 32 years old Nitrates directive and the market of this sustainable fertiliser struggles to develop due to a lack of legal certainty. Nonetheless, digestate has the potential to significantly replace synthetic/inorganic nitrogen fertilisers as produced based on natural gas, thereby improving both the environmental impact as well as economic and geopolitical self-reliance.

In the framework of the upcoming publication of the Integrated Nutrient Management Action Plan (INMAP), we call on the Commission **to allow and facilitate the safe use of digestate and employ the INMAP to provide guidelines for its usage.**

Organic fertilisers partially or entirely derived from animal manure through anaerobic digestion, known as digestate, represents a key tool to **substitute synthetic/inorganic fertilisers, increase on-farm circularity and make food systems resilient as they depend on locally available resources while preserving the environment and waters in Europe.** In line with the objectives of the EU Green deal, digestate contributes to recycling nutrients, increasing resource efficiency and when managed adequately, avoids nutrients losses and maintains soil fertility

In the framework of the INMAP, we urge the Commission to:

- allow for a **temporary exemption** from the Nitrates Directive limit, in the short term, so that **the safe use of digestate is allowed above the limit of 170 kg of nitrogen per hectare per year**.
- propose a **revision of Annex III of the Nitrates Directives** to allow for a **permanent exemption** of digestate from the Nitrates Directive limit in the medium term. The Expert group on the implementation of the nitrates Directive or a dedicated expert group should **propose a set of guiding agronomic practices to mitigate any potential environmental risks**.

It must be noted that digestate is the resulting product of a controlled biological process of anaerobic digestion whose purpose is the transformation of the easily fermentable organic fraction into biogas. The biological transformations carried out by the bacteria also determine profound modifications of the substrates subjected to the biological process, the result of which is a **biologically stable matrix with excellent soil improver and fertiliser properties**.

Digestate cannot be compared or assimilated with livestock manure for the following reasons:

- Anaerobic digestion is a biotechnological process that deeply transforms zootechnical effluents into another product.
- Livestock manure – unlike digestate – still contains fermentable fractions that, by degrading in the soil, can lead to the partial mineralization of organic nitrogen with a risk of nitrate leaching.
- The fertilising effects of digestate are specific: digestate contains stabilised organic matter, whose carbon-to-nitrogen ratio (C/N) is generally very close to soil organic matter as well as ammonia which is a readily available source of nitrogen for plants. With the application of a specific amount of digestate, calibrated to the nitrogen need of the crop, comes a positive net environmental balance since the nitrogen content of digestate is about 90% efficient. This efficiency reduces the risk of nitrate leaching into groundwaters to a minimum.

3. Policy Brief - Soil Monitoring Law.

FEEDBACK REPLY PROPOSAL FOR A SOIL MONITORING LAW

The co-signatories include two European sister projects which aim at facilitating the uptake of circular fertilisers: **FER-PLAY** and **NOVAFERT**.

Healthy soils are essential for life on Earth and provide a variety of vital ecosystems services such as food security, water purification, biodiversity habitats, nutrient cycling and carbon sequestration. Yet today 60 to 70% of soil in the EU is estimated to be in unhealthy condition leading to severe risks for the environment, economy and society. However, sustainable soil management, together with the restoration of unhealthy soils, could contribute to reversing the critical situation.

The European Union urgently needed a clear and effective regulatory framework to protect and restore EU soil. FER-PLAY and NOVAFERT welcome the **proposal for a Soil Monitoring Law** published on the 5th of July which is a first step towards achieving the goal of having all soils in healthy condition in Europe by 2050.

The proposal of the European Commission provides a solid monitoring and assessment framework for soil health and sets the basic principles to define sustainable soil management (SSM) and regeneration practices as well as remediate contaminated sites. To restore soil health, SSM practices will need to be gradually implemented on all EU managed soils and regeneration practices on unhealthy soils. As indicated in Annex III of the proposal, these practices must be compliant with SSM principles which include the principle "e.": "*when fertilization is applied, ensure adaptation to the needs of the plant and trees at the given location and in the given period, and to the condition of soil and **prioritize circular solutions that enrich the organic content***".

FER-PLAY and NOVAFERT welcome the inclusion of this SSM principle which recognises the importance of using circular fertilisers with recycled nutrients and soil improvement properties. One of the main drivers of the degradation of soils and of the ecosystems depending on these soils (e.g. water bodies), is related to unsustainable/traditional fertilisation which has resulted in contamination (by heavy metals and excess of nutrients), increased water demand, and poor provision of organic constituents to the soil. Russia's war on Ukraine has destabilised global food security making it essential for the EU to secure fertile soils by requiring the production and use of fertilisers from local renewable sources. Additionally circular fertilisers play a crucial role in soil remediation processes by enriching soil organic carbon.

Given the level of soil degradation in Europe and its potential impacts, FER-PLAY and NOVAFERT believe the Soil Monitoring Law must:

- **Include binding targets for soil health in Article 1:** in the current proposal, the Directive does not provide any roadmap, intermediary binding targets or mandatory national plans to ensure that the 2050 soil health objective is reached in due time.

- **Make the implementation of SSM and regeneration practices mandatory in Article 10:** Member States only have the obligation to define SSM and regeneration practices, not to implement them, which is not sufficient to ensure that soil is restored at the needed pace. Additionally, it is important to require building capacity regarding SSM at relevant districts at MS level. The practices should be adapted to the specific local, climatic, and social-economic conditions, as well as land uses and soil type.
- **Shorten the time allowed to identify the potentially contaminated soils in Article 13:** The Identification of potentially contaminated soils shall be done within the first 3 to 4 years after entry into force, to allow competent authorities to take due action as to remediation and restoration actions. Moreover, this is not in line with the 4 years requirement set out in Article 16, paragraph 1, leading to inconsistency to enforcement of the law.
- **Identify an “environmental safety” threshold in Article 15:** The EU Commission shall identify minimum “environmental safety” thresholds below which Member States cannot go beyond in terms of “unacceptable risk for human health” resulting from contaminated sites. Leaving full flexibility for Member States to define what is acceptable and what is not will create different health criteria across the Union.
- **Request the publication by the European Commission of a specific technical guidance with examples of effective SSM and regeneration practices:** SSM principles are useful but Member States need more information on all the innovative practices that they could implement to sustainably manage and regenerate soils. This guidance could present the most suitable practices according to the specific local and climatic conditions as well as land uses and soil types. This guidance is also key given the limited timeframe available for the transition towards healthier soils.
- **Support the implementation of SSM and regeneration practices in other EU legislations and remove any remaining regulatory barrier for the uptake of these practices.** The Common Agricultural Policy should further promote the use of circular fertilisers as an eco-scheme or even as a “good agricultural and environmental condition” (GAEC). Any other barriers faced by these fertilisers in the Fertilising Products Regulation, the Sewage Sludge Directive, the Animal By-Products Regulation or the Nitrate Directive should be tackled.
- **Request Member States, through the designated competent authority at each district level, to provide input to a shared EU database of SSM practices used/adopted to remediate/restore soil functions in Chapter 3 (Sustainable Soil Management).** This database shall be made publicly available to all competent authorities in order to foster cross-border knowledge and practice sharing on SSM practices in action. Depending on the severity of the contamination or soil depletion status, databases on adopted measures at soil district level shall be elaborated to allow cross -fertilization of experiences within and across EU Member States.
- **Include mechanisms to evaluate the impact of unhealthy soils on linked ecosystems and earth compartments.** This is for example the case of water bodies affected by nutrient contamination sourced from unsustainable fertilization in agricultural soils. For this objective, environmental indicators, such as the grey hydric footprint, have proven to be effective.
- **Increase the importance in the law of the circular fertilisers** (and of choosing the adequate and sustainable agriculture inputs in general), as a key factor to reduce

degradation, improve soil health, increase resilience and contribute to the objectives of the proposed Directive and other EU environmental ambitions (e.g. carbon sequestration, reduction of fertilisers dependency...).

4. Policy Recommendations for Circular Fertilisers Market Uptake: Insights from FER-PLAY and NOVAFERT workshop

The circular fertilisers market represents a significant opportunity to enhance sustainability in agricultural practices by closing nutrient and organic matter loops, promoting resource efficiency, and reducing dependence on conventional chemical fertilisers. However, several policy barriers must be addressed to facilitate the widespread adoption of circular fertilisers across Europe. This policy recommendation document summarises key regulatory challenges and proposes actionable recommendations aimed at overcoming these barriers and supporting the growth of the circular fertilisers market.

Key Regulatory Barriers and Recommendations

1. Fertilising Products Regulation (FPR)

- **Current Barrier:** A significant number of feedstocks that are used for the production of circular fertilisers are excluded from the scope of the FPR, leading to a major discrepancy with other legislations. The incomplete implementation of the regulation further hampers the EU market uptake of circular fertilisers.
- **Recommendation:** The FPR should undergo a thorough review, as planned for 2025, to ensure that it accommodates a wider range of circular fertilisers and operational requirements for all categories. The scope of the regulation must be expanded to include the feedstocks that are used to produce these fertilisers, and implementation guidelines should be clarified to remove ambiguities and allow for greater market access.

2. Organic Farming Regulation

- **Current Barrier:** Circular fertilisers such as struvite face challenges in meeting the strict requirements under the Organic Farming Regulation. This is also the case of digestate due to the lack of definition of key terms like "factory farming."
- **Recommendation:** A revision of the Organic Farming Regulation is needed to clarify the standards for circular fertilisers and introduce a clear definition of "factory farming." This would improve the applicability of circular fertilisers in organic farming and contribute to their broader acceptance within the sector.

3. Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)

- **Current Barrier:** The CAP currently lacks sufficient ambition and enforceable measures at the national level, which limits its effectiveness in driving the uptake of circular fertilisers in agriculture.
- **Recommendation:** To enhance nutrient and organic matter recycling and the adoption of circular fertilisers, the CAP must introduce mandatory measures for the use of circular fertilisers within the CAP Strategic Plans. Additionally, greater emphasis should be placed on aligning CAP with sustainability goals, promoting circularity, and ensuring consistency with national policies.

Key Drivers to Enhance Nutrient Recycling and Support Circular Fertilisers Rollout

1. Revitalise the Integrated Nutrient Management (INM) Action Plan

A comprehensive action plan is needed to strengthen the EU's approach to INM, ensuring efficient use and recycling of nutrients throughout the agricultural system. The action plan should focus on scaling nutrient recovery technologies and creating market incentives for circular fertilisers.

2. Implement Nutrient and Organic Matter Recycling Targets

Setting clear, binding targets for nutrient and organic matter recycling in agriculture will incentivize the adoption of circular fertilisers. These targets should be aligned with broader EU sustainability goals and provide a clear roadmap for national governments and stakeholders in the fertiliser industry.

3. Establish Fiscal Tools to support market uptake

Financial incentives such as subsidies, tax breaks, or research grants are necessary to support the development and scaling of circular fertiliser technologies. These tools should be designed to reduce the financial burden on producers and farmers transitioning to circular fertilisers.

4. Integrate Agriculture into the EU Emissions Trading Scheme (ETS)

The principles of carbon farming and the potential for renewable energy production as well as opportunities for reducing GHG emissions (e.g. from organic waste, or the agrifood value chain) could be further incentivized by integrating the achieved CO₂e_q benefits in the tradeable credit system. This would allow to generate traction from other industrial sectors (which are in need of GHG reductions) towards making the agrifood value chain itself more sustainable.

5. Strengthen Research and Development (R&D) Efforts

Increased funding and collaboration in R&D are critical to advancing technologies for nutrient recovery and improving the quality of circular fertilisers. EU research projects should focus on identifying best practices for circular fertiliser production, enhancing scalability, and ensuring quality standards. Collaboration between research bodies, industry players, and policymakers will accelerate the transition to circular fertilisers.

Challenges Identified in the Roundtable Discussions

1. Lack of Knowledge on Best Practices

A key challenge is the widespread lack of knowledge on best practices for circular fertiliser production and application across Europe. Local authorities and farmers often face barriers related to insufficient knowledge and guidance on effective circular fertiliser use.

2. Contaminant Thresholds and Scientific Evidence

Contaminant thresholds for circular fertilisers need to be re-established based on scientific evidence, considering organic and inorganic forms of contaminants and their relevance to different farming scenarios.

3. Need for Brokered Interactions Between Research and Policymakers

There is a strong need for more brokered interaction between EU research projects and policymakers at both EU and local levels. Such interactions will ensure that technological advancements and novel insights are quickly translated into actionable policy recommendations and help close the gap between scientific developments and regulatory frameworks.

To achieve the full potential of circular fertilisers and contribute to the EU's sustainability goals, a comprehensive and coordinated approach is needed. By addressing regulatory barriers, promoting research and development, and implementing targeted fiscal tools, the EU can enhance nutrient recycling, promote the uptake of circular fertilisers, and support a more sustainable agricultural sector. Policy reforms in these areas are crucial to ensure that circular fertilisers are integrated into mainstream agricultural practices, helping the EU transition to a circular economy.

Recommendations Summary:

- Review the FPR to enhance the practical applicability of its existing requirements and expand it to accommodate a broader range of circular fertilisers.
- Revise the Organic Farming Regulation to clarify the use of circular fertilisers and update the definition of "factory farming."
- Integrate mandatory measures for circular fertilisers in the CAP Strategic Plans.
- Revitalise the principles of the INM Plan into a new targeted action plan and set clear recycling targets.
- Implement fiscal tools such as subsidies and grants to support the circular fertiliser market.
- Include agriculture in the EU Emissions Trading Scheme (ETS).
- Strengthen EU R&D efforts to support innovation in nutrient recycling technologies.

By implementing these policy recommendations, the European Union can drive the market uptake of circular fertilisers, contribute to environmental sustainability, and enhance the resilience of its agricultural sector.

5. Conclusions

The Deliverable 3.6 of the NOVAFERT project consolidates key policy recommendations aimed at accelerating the uptake of circular fertilisers across the EU, with a particular focus on digestate and RENURE products. The joint position paper and stakeholder engagements have directly contributed to advancing regulatory dialogue, most notably within the framework of the Integrated Nutrient Management Action Plan (INMAP). As of March 2025, the European Commission is actively reviewing provisions of the Nitrates Directive, with growing support for allowing temporary and potentially permanent exemptions for digestate use beyond the 170 kg N/ha/year limit. This signals a shift toward greater legal recognition of digestate as a distinct, safe, and effective fertiliser within circular nutrient systems.

In parallel, progress on the EU Soil Monitoring Law reflects many of the recommendations made by NOVAFERT and FER-PLAY, including the inclusion of binding targets for soil health by 2050 and a shortened timeline for identifying contaminated soils. These regulatory advancements demonstrate that stakeholder-driven proposals are being taken into serious consideration at the EU level. The integration of circular fertilisers into sustainable soil management and nutrient recovery strategies is gaining traction, and De 3.6 serves as a timely and evidence-based input to support the final shaping of these crucial legislative instruments. Continued engagement will be essential to ensure that upcoming revisions to the Fertilising Products Regulation, the Common Agricultural Policy, and the Organic Farming Regulation fully reflect the needs of a resilient, circular European agricultural sector.